

Influence of Knowledge Management Process on Organizational Performance: Case Study of Jordan Telecom Group Orange

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Abstract:

This study aimed to identify the impact of knowledge management process on organizational performance: Case Study of Jordan Telecom Group Orange, a sample consisted of 80 employees in orange company, the study found: there is a significant influence of knowledge acquisition on the organizational performance, and there is impact of a significant knowledge distribution, knowledge interpretation, and organizational memory. In the end, the study recommended that the company use knowledge base systems continuously to keep of tacit and explicit knowledge

Keyword: knowledge management process, organizational performance, tacit and explicit knowledge

Introduction

During the last period, the world witnessed the importance of knowledge management, which was reflected in the administrative performance of the companies, which led to the continuity, improvement, and development of these companies and transformed them into a process more suitable for the rapid changes in the business world. Its role has been to build management systems based on intellectual assets, thus improving the product and service provided to customers and in view of the role of knowledge management in achieving the objectives of the organization has been increased . The knowledge management processes and their impact on organizational performance in the Orange Communications Group.

Important study

The importance of the study comes from the importance of knowledge management process on organizational performance, and its role in the interpretation and classification of data and information both internally and externally in order to support management functions, giving advanced solutions for managers, helping administrators to take correct decision in company , improve strategic planning level in organizations.

Study objective

This study aim dynamics of knowledge management process impact on the organizational performance in the Orange Communications Group, we can determine the following goals:

- 1-identify the dimensions of knowledge management process impact on the organization performance.
- 2- Make suggestions to the organizations to enhance the organizational performance through the improvement in knowledge management processes

Hypothesis

To answer the questions, the research depends on the following main hypothesis: There is a significant effect at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) of knowledge management process on organizational performance. The main hypothesis subdivided into the following Assumptions:

Hypothesis1: knowledge acquisition has a significant influence on organizational performance **Hypothesis2:** knowledge distribution has a significant influence on organizational performance

Hypothesis 3: knowledge interpretation has a significant influence on organizational performance

Hypothesis 4: organizational knowledge memory has a significant influence on organizational performance

Study model

Figure 1 shows that the independent variables in this study are four knowledge management process (knowledge acquisition, knowledge distribution, knowledge interpretation, organizational memory) termed as criteria of which influence on organizational performance in the Jordan Orange Communications Group.

Figure (1) study model

Previous study

Knowledge takes a form of resources such as land, workers, and capital (Rašula et al, 2012). Knowledge management has many types, but the most known type is tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge as mentioned by Polanyi, 1967 *"we can know more than we can tell."* Knowledge management is a dynamic phenomenon that has an impact on the most dimension of management. Knowledge management has many definition and concepts as *"the systematic process of finding, selecting, organizing, distilling, and presenting information in a way that improves an employee's comprehension in a specific area of interest"* (Mertins et al ,2003). One knowledge management process is knowledge sharing an attractive term that deals with management, psychology, and Human Behavior. Knowledge sharing is a process of share information, ideas and skills with others explicitly as physical activity or over medium (i.e., Social Networks, Radio, TV ... etc.). Davenport and Prusak (1998) describe knowledge as "a fluid mix of framed experience, value, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. Nonaka and Takeuchi, (1995) defined knowledge as "dynamic human processes of justifying personal belief towards the 'truth.'" .Burke 2000 defines knowledge recursively as "meaning derived from information and other knowledge" .Sveiby, (1997) considered knowledge is the capacity to act within context.

This paper focuses on four-knowledge management process as following: knowledge acquisition is the process the company uses for obtaining new information and knowledge ,also knowledge distribution it comprises the dissemination of acquired knowledge between different individuals or units within a company, This process is principally accomplished through informal interactions among the employees of the company .while, knowledge interpretation is processes required in order that information is understood and assimilated by employees in order to transform it into a new common knowledge .finally , knowledge organizational memory is both the tacit and explicit knowledge stored in the database of the organization and made available for the future use (Asheyh and U Syed ,2016

Organizational performance

According (Ashley and used 2016) the Organizational performance define is the indicators of performance of an organization can be broadly categorized into the Operational performance, Financial performance and Non-financial performance factors and develop and improve the performance of individuals and teams and therefore organizations.The term "Performance Management " refers to an integrated, systematic approach to improving

organizational performance to achieve strategic aims and promote an organization's mission and values. In that sense, organizational performance management is quite different from individual performance management which specifically targets the personal performance of an employee although the latter comprises an essential part of the overall organizational performance framework. In fact, a Performance Management system aims at improving the results of people's efforts by linking these to the organization's goals and objectives. It is, ideally, the means through which employees' performance can be improved by ensuring appropriate recognition and reward for their efforts, and by improving communication, learning and working arrangements (Ashayh and Usyed, 2016). Performance management is a process for establishing a shared understanding about what is to be achieved and how it is to be achieved, and an approach to managing and developing people that improve individual, team and organizational performance (Armstrong, 2009). The organizational performance refers to the ability of an enterprise to achieve such objectives, quality, good financial result, product and large market share (Koontz and Donnell, 1993). Performance of organizations is related to the profitability of the organizations in terms of its growth and profit both in the long and short-term (Amal and Nosheen, 2015).

Jordan Telecom Group

In 1996, the TRA was established and transformed a telecommunications corporation into a company under government with financial and administrative independence, and registered in a register in 1997 under the name of telecommunications company / 10 / companies on 08 Jordanian. The company started its operations with a capital of 530-denier A under its new name in 1997 as a major supplier of services Communications in Jordan, where the company is running Jordan's technological infrastructure. In 2006, it was Direct Jordanian Telecom's strategy to merge with companies Affiliated Company on behalf of Jordan Telecom Group, and early on Orange 2007 started the brand-bearing group.

Methodology

Population and sample

The target population for this study is the knowledge management process in Communication Companies in Jordan; the orange company was chosen as a case study, 80 questionnaires were distributed; the response rate was 88% (71 usable responses).

Hypotheses

The objective of this study is to test the following hypotheses:

- 1- Enabler knowledge acquisition has a significant influence on organization performance.
- 2- Enabler knowledge distribution has a significant influence on organization performance.
- 3- Enabler knowledge interpretation has a significant influence on organization performance.
- 4- Enabler knowledge memory has a significant influence on organization performance.

Data Collection

- Secondary data was collected based on the finding of published papers, articles, books, previous studies, and the World Wide Web.

- Primary data collection was carried out using a self-designed questionnaire. This adopted instrument comprises seven sections. The first section covers demographic information (Gender, education, experience of working), the second section contains (5) items measuring the level of availability of knowledge acquisition in the orange company, the third section contains (5) items measuring the availability of knowledge distribution in orange company, the fourth section contains (5) items measuring the support and importance of knowledge interpretation in the orange company, the fifth section contains (5) items measuring the Organizational performance in orange company.

Validity and Reliability

The questionnaires used five-point Likert's scales anchored by 'strongly disagree' and 'strongly agree' to measure the index in three dimensions of development management. Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the reliability of each of the measure. The Alpha of all scales exceeded the cut-off 0.60 recommended by (Sekaran 2003).

Table 1 showed that the Cronbach's Alpha for the study was between 0.70 to 0.80. In general, which registered acceptable.

Table (1) Cronbach's Alpha for Research Variable

Variable	Number of items	Alpha
knowledge acquisition	5	(0.851)
, knowledge distribution	5	(0.846)
knowledge interpretation	5	(0.821)
Knowledge memory	5	(0.882)

The purpose of data collection, the permission was obtained from the administration office. Latest statistics on a number of staff for each department were gathered from the head of each unit in every department. The researcher then obtained permission and cooperation of the head of each unit to identify respondent and eventually distribute the questionnaires to the respondents. The Questionnaires were sent to 80 employees working in the company. Only (71) were returned. The overall response rate for this study was 88%. This is regarded as relatively high since the respondents are managers and they supposed to be too busy to answer Questionnaire. A Questionnaire was sent to respondents such as managers, department head, Assistant managers, employees currently working in the orange company.

The Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data. Descriptive techniques such as Frequencies, Means, standard deviations Percentages, Coefficient of correlation, were used to describe variables and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypothesis of the stud

Statistical Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

Analysis of personal and functional characteristics

We used several questions to find out the distribution of the study sample, according to personal and functional characteristics, Such as gender, education, work experience.

Table (2) shows these properties Demographic distribution of the Respondent

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	50	70.42
female	21	29.58
Total	71	%100
AGE		
22- 25	4	5.64
26- 30	6	8.45
31- 40	28	39.44
Great than 40	33	46.47
Education qualification	71	100%
Diploma	20	28.17
Graduate	40	56.33
master	8	11.27
PHD	3	4.23
Work experience	71	%100
Less than two years	2	2.81
3-5years	6	8.45
6-10 years	10	14.09
More than 10years	53	74.65

Characteristics of the study sample

Table (3) shows that most of the respondents were of the total number of males (50) or (70.42) this indicates that most individual who occupies administrative levels are male. As noted from the table, most of the sample were included

the categories of 31 years and over, where the number of sample members within these categories (61) individuals, and their proportion (89.4%), and we infer from this percentage indicates that the company focuses on the youth category

Experience .also shows that most of the respondents are from

(65.33%) This indicates that the company is interested in recruiting individuals from campaign First university degrees and above. The years of experience were

Indicate that most of the respondents are in the middle category (from 10 years and over), where they reached 74.65% the ratio refers to the company's focus on those with high experience.

Hypothesis testing

Is evident from Table (4) having the effect of a statistical significance of knowledge management processes combined to organization performance of it, (Orange) organization performance Jordan Telecom Group level of significance (0.00), a (T) depending on the height of the values and promotes that ($\alpha \leq$ statistically significant at the level of (0.05). The results showed that the rise in the values of knowledge organization memory was ranked first in the achievement of organizational performance, followed by the process of distribution and acquisition of knowledge, and then the process of knowledge interpretation, which ranked last in achieving the organizational performance of Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) at following:

Table (3) Results of the strength factor of knowledge management processes on the organizational performance of Jordan Telecom Group

Dimension	B	Standard error	Beta	T value	Level of significant
Knowledge acquisition	15	0.034	.21	6.452	0.00
Knowledge distribution	17	0.033	.18	8.422	0.00
Knowledge interpretation	14	0.035	.19	5.333	0.01
TKnowledge organization memory	19	0.031	.26	9.246	0.00

To answer the questions, the research depends on the following main hypothesis: There is a significant effect at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) of knowledge management process on organizational performance. The main hypothesis subdivided into the following Assumptions:

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To answer the validity of these assumptions have been applied T values to the supported table (4)| shows that

Table (4) T-statistic of hypothetical

	Original sample	Simple Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error	T statics	Hypothesis
	0.253	0.244	0.0442	0.0442	5.723	Supported
	0.432	0.426	0.0603	0.0603	7.164	Supported
	0.421	0.416	0.0451	0.0451	9.334	Supported
	0.2214	0.2124	0.0503	0.0503	4.401	Supported

1%signifince > 2.5)

Finding

- The level of application of knowledge management processes in Jordan Telecom Group is relatively high and has a significant impact on organizational performance .This high level may be due to the flow and ease of communication between these levels, the strength of the relations between presidents and subordinates, and the mutual trust between them this result is consistent with the study
- Knowledge acquisition, knowledge distribution, knowledge interpretation, and knowledge memory have a clear impact on organizational performance, which was evident by supporting the hypotheses of the study.
- The success of all companies now depends on the operation of knowledge and knowledge in addition to digital intelligence, and it is clear that the company depends on all its transactions on the digital technological progress.
- These results support the knowledge management literature, which states that knowledge management processes are more effective in increasing the length of service and thus increasing organizational performance.
- The knowledge management process helps employee towards improved organizational performance.

References

- i. *Armstrong, Michael (2009), Handbook of Performance Management An Evidence-based Guide to Delivering High Performance, 4th edition, London, Kogan Page, e-Book.*
- ii. *Amal khon ,nosheen adnan ,impact of leadership style on Organizational Performance , international journal of management sciences vol,2 N 11 2014 .*
- iii. *Ayesha Ahmad , U Syed Aktharsha (2016) Influence of Knowledge Management Processes on Organizational Performance in Service Sector: An Empirical Study, International Journal of Business and Management Invention Volume 5 Issue 11 || November. 2016 || PP—28-35.*
- iv. *Burke, M. (2000). Thinking together: new forms of thought system for a revolution in military affairs, Defense Science and Technology Organization.*
- v. *-Davenport, T., &Prusak, L. (1998).Working knowledge .how organization manage what they know. Harvard business school press.*
- vi. *J. Rašula, V. B. Vukšić, and M. I. Štemberger, The impact of knowledge management on organizational performance. Economic and Business Review, 14(2), 2012, 147–168.*
- vii. *Mertins, K., Heisig, P., & Vorbeck, J. (Eds.). (2003). Knowledge management: concepts and best practices. Springer Science & Business Media.*
 - a. *-Koontz,H.& Donnell,C.(1993). Introduction to Management New-York: McGraw-Hill.*
- viii. *Nonaka, I.and Takeuchi, H. (1995), the knowledge creating company, oxford University press, New York, NY.*
- ix. *Sveiby, K., A Knowledge-based Theory of the Firm To guide Strategy Formulation Article for Journal of Intellectual Capital vol 2, Nr4. Journal of Intellectual Capital Highly Commended Paper Award for 1997. Internet version. www.sveiby.com.*
- x. *Polanyi, Michael (1967) the study of man Chicago .university of Chicago process.*
- xi. *Www. Orange .JO*